

Enhancing Iterative Proportional Fitting for Efficient and Scalable Synthetic Population Generation

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Abstract

The Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) algorithm is widely used for survey weighting and synthetic population generation. While efficient in low-dimensional settings, IPF struggles with zero-cell issues in sparse contingency tables and becomes computationally infeasible as dimensionality increases. To address these challenges, we propose a blockwise IPF framework that partitions variables into smaller, correlated feature groups, applying IPF independently within each group. Real-world synthetic population generation experiments show that this method greatly improves computational efficiency and scalability in high-dimensional settings while still maintaining a reasonable fit to marginal distributions and preserving inter-variable dependencies comparable to standard IPF. We also introduce a hybrid framework that integrates IPF with generative models such as Bayesian networks and Tabular Variational Autoencoders. This approach ensures accurate marginal fitting while enhancing realism and diversity in synthetic populations. Our contributions improve upon standard IPF and generative models in advancing synthetic population modeling.

Key Words: Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF), blockwise IPF, synthetic population generation, high-dimensional data, contingency tables, marginal constraints, scalability, computational efficiency, survey weighting, generative models, Bayesian networks

1. Introduction

The Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) algorithm remains one of the most widely used techniques for calibrating surveys and generating synthetic populations by adjusting micro-sample contingency tables to match population marginal data distributions [Deming and Stephan, 1940, Beckman et al., 1996, Agresti, 2012]. Despite its simplicity and theoretical foundations, standard IPF becomes computationally infeasible in high-dimensional applications due to the exponential growth in the size of contingency tables, a phenomenon commonly known as the curse of dimensionality [Borysov et al., 2018]. Sparse multiway tables further exacerbate instability and zero-cell issues, which reduces the algorithm’s ability to recover reliable joint distributions when sample sizes are limited [Sun and Erath, 2015].

Numerous adaptations—such as Iterative Proportional Updating (IPU) [Ye et al., 2009], Hierarchical IPF (HIPF) [Mueller and Axhausen, 2011], and sparse-list IPF [Pritchard and Miller, 2012]—have attempted to address scalability and memory constraints. More recently, probabilistic and deep learning approaches such as Bayesian networks [Sun and Erath, 2015], Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [Borysov et al., 2018], and copula-based models [Jeong et al., 2016, Li et al., 2020, Jutras-Dubé et al., 2024] have been proposed to model complex dependencies directly and resolve scalability issues. However, these frameworks often perform best with continuous data and struggle to enforce marginal constraints or preserve logical consistency when applied to categorical or mixed-type data.

To overcome these challenges while retaining the strengths of IPF, we introduce two complementary extensions. The first is a *Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF)* framework, which partitions the variable space into correlated subsets and applies standard IPF within each block. This “divide-and-conquer” strategy mitigates computational burden and alleviates sparsity issues

by exploiting lower-dimensional margins that remain well-populated and statistically meaningful.

The second is a *Hybrid IPF–Generative Framework* designed to integrate IPF with modern generative modeling techniques. In this framework, IPF-derived sampling weights are used to guide the training of generative models (e.g., Bayesian networks), allowing them to produce diverse, out-of-sample agents while maintaining alignment with known population marginals. This hybrid approach is model-agnostic and bridges the gap between traditional population constraint-based and machine-learning-based synthesis to achieve both representational diversity and distributional consistency.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the methodological foundations of the proposed Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF) and hybrid frameworks, together with their algorithmic implementations. Section 3 presents the experimental design and results pertaining to synthetic population generation case studies utilizing data sets from the American Community Survey for Maryland and Texas. These numerical experiments offer an empirical evaluation of the proposed methods. Section 4 reports the empirical findings and discusses the comparative insights and observed trade-offs among methods. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with key takeaways and future research directions.

2. Methods

2.1 The Blockwise IPF Framework

The Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF) framework extends the classical IPF algorithm to high-dimensional contingency tables by decomposing the problem into smaller, tractable subproblems. Standard IPF adjusts an initial joint distribution in the form of a contingency table of arbitrary dimension to match known marginals but becomes computationally infeasible when the number of variables is large. While effective in low dimensions, IPF becomes computationally infeasible as the number of variables grows, since the joint table expands exponentially. BIPF mitigates this challenge through a three-component framework consisting of: (1) feature clustering, (2) blockwise IPF fitting, and (3) aggregation of block-level results.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the Blockwise IPF (BIPF) framework, showing its three main components: feature clustering, blockwise fitting, and result aggregation.

2.1.1 Stage I: Feature clustering via community detection

The first stage partitions the variable set $\{X_1, \dots, X_p\}$ into K disjoint blocks $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_K\}$ such that variables are strongly dependent within each block but approximately independent across blocks. To achieve this, we employ Exploratory Graph Analysis (EGA) implemented in the EGAnet package [Golino and Epskamp, 2017, Christensen et al., 2024], which estimates a partial-correlation network and identifies feature communities using algorithms such as Louvain or Leiden. This procedure yields interpretable clusters that preserve essential dependencies while enabling computational scalability. The network-based approach ensures that feature groups are internally cohesive and externally independent, a property desirable for BIPF to work.

2.1.2 Stage II: blockwise IPF fitting

Once variable groups are defined, standard IPF is applied independently within each block to adjust local contingency tables T_k to their respective marginal targets. The classical IPF algorithm for a two-way table proceeds as follows.

Let $X = [x_{ij}]$ be a non-negative $I \times J$ contingency table representing joint frequencies of two categorical variables. Suppose we are given row sums $\{r_i\}_{i=1}^I$ and column sums $\{c_j\}_{j=1}^J$, which

represent desired marginal distributions for the fitted table $\hat{X} = [\hat{x}_{ij}]$. The IPF algorithm seeks a solution table \hat{X} that satisfies

$$\hat{x}_{i+} = \sum_{j=1}^J \hat{x}_{ij} = r_i \quad \text{for all } i = 1, \dots, I, \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{x}_{+j} = \sum_{i=1}^I \hat{x}_{ij} = c_j \quad \text{for all } j = 1, \dots, J. \quad (1)$$

Starting from a non-negative initial estimate $x_{ij}^{(0)} := x_{ij} \geq 0$ (often a uniform table or observed counts), IPF proceeds iteratively by scaling rows and columns in alternation. Each iteration t involves two steps ($t \geq 1$):

1. Row scaling:

$$x_{ij}^{(2t-1)} = x_{ij}^{(2t-2)} \cdot \frac{r_i}{\sum_{j=1}^J x_{ij}^{(2t-2)}}, \quad \text{for each } i. \quad (2)$$

2. Column scaling:

$$x_{ij}^{(2t)} = x_{ij}^{(2t-1)} \cdot \frac{c_j}{\sum_{i=1}^I x_{ij}^{(2t-1)}}, \quad \text{for each } j. \quad (3)$$

This process is repeated until convergence is achieved, at which point the solution \hat{x}_{ij} becomes $x_{ij}^{(2t)}$, the last state of the adjusted table. Each iteration brings the current table closer to the target marginals while preserving the initial structure of associations (e.g., odds ratios).

A common choice of convergence criterion [Jeong et al., 2016] is

$$\max_i \{|\hat{x}_{i+} - r_i|\} + \max_j \{|\hat{x}_{+j} - c_j|\} < \epsilon, \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is the tolerance level for convergence, typically a very small value such as 10^{-6} , which measures the maximum deviation from the target marginal distributions along all axes. Bishop et al. [2007], within the context of using IPF as a maximum likelihood estimator for log-linear models, discusses other stopping rules. For well-posed problems, this procedure converges to a unique solution [Csiszár, 1975].

This procedure extends naturally to multi-way (high-dimensional) contingency tables, where the two-step scaling process at each iteration is generalized to multiple dimensions.

2.1.3 Stage III: Observation-level weight generation and aggregation

For each observation, BIPF computes a set of block-level sampling weights based on the ratio of adjusted to empirical block frequencies or probabilities. After convergence, the adjusted block table \hat{T}_k and its original copy T_k are used to compute a block-specific weight tensor:

$$\mathbf{W}_k = \frac{\hat{T}_k}{T_k}, \quad (5)$$

where the division is element-wise. For each observation i with categorical profile x_{i,B_k} in the sample \mathcal{D} , the corresponding block weight is

$$w_i^{(k)} = \mathbf{W}_k(x_{i,B_k}) = \frac{\hat{T}_k(x_{i,B_k})}{T_k(x_{i,B_k})}.$$

The final step integrates block-specific adjustments into a unified solution. We propose two implementation variants: a naive BIPF and a sequential BIPF. The *Naive BIPF* combines block-specific weights $w^{(k)}$ multiplicatively under the assumption of independence across blocks to form the global weight vector \mathbf{w} given by Equation 6. This approach is simple, efficient, and order-invariant.

$$w = \prod_{k=1}^K w^{(k)}. \quad (6)$$

These weights re-align the empirical distribution with the population constraints while preserving sample-level structure. They can be used for weighted estimation, resampling, or direct generation of synthetic populations without materializing the full high-dimensional contingency table.

The *Sequential BIPF* (Algorithm 2) relaxes the blockwise independence assumption by reweighting the sample sequentially after each block-level IPF adjustment. This iterative procedure allows marginal constraints across all variables to be progressively satisfied and is particularly suited for synthetic population generation tasks where inter-block dependencies exist and a global sampling weight is not required.

Algorithm 1: Naive Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (N-BIPF)

Input: Dataset \mathcal{D} with n observations and p categorical variables; target marginals $\{M_j\}_{j=1}^p$; population size N .

Output: Global observation weight vector \mathbf{w} .

Step 1: Partition the variables $\{X_1, \dots, X_p\}$ into K disjoint blocks $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_K\}$ via feature clustering (e.g., EGA).

Step 2: Initialize $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathbf{1}_n$.

Step 3: for each block $B_k \in \mathcal{B}$ Construct contingency table T_k for variables in B_k .

Apply standard IPF to T_k using marginal constraints M_k to obtain \hat{T}_k .

Compute block-specific observation weights:

$$w_i^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{T}_k(x_{i,B_k})}{T_k(x_{i,B_k})}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

Update global weights: $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathbf{w} \circ \mathbf{w}^{(k)}$.

Step 4: Normalize $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow N \times \mathbf{w} / \sum_i w_i$.

return \mathbf{w}

Algorithm 2: Sequential (Reweighting) Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (S-BIPF)

Input: Dataset \mathcal{D} ; target marginals $\{M_j\}$; variable blocks $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_K\}$.

Output: Reweighted dataset \mathcal{D}_w .

Step 1: Initialize $\mathcal{D}_w \leftarrow \mathcal{D}$.

Step 2: for each block $B_k \in \mathcal{B}$ Construct contingency table T_k from \mathcal{D}_w .

Apply standard IPF on T_k using marginals M_k to obtain \hat{T}_k .

Compute block-level weights

$$w_i^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{T}_k(x_{i,B_k})}{T_k(x_{i,B_k})}.$$

Reweight or resample \mathcal{D}_w according to $\mathbf{w}^{(k)}$ before proceeding to the next block.

return \mathcal{D}_w

Remarks: S-BIPF relaxes the independence assumption by propagating block adjustments sequentially. It improves cross-block consistency but may be block order-dependent.

2.2 Hybrid IPF–Generative Modeling Framework

Generating synthetic populations that both satisfy known marginal distributions and preserve structural diversity remains challenging. Traditional statistical methods such as IPF guarantee marginal consistency but often replicate patterns present in the seed sample, limiting diversity and out-of-sample realism. Conversely, modern generative models (e.g., Bayesian networks, VAEs, GANs) can reproduce complex joint dependencies but typically lack mechanisms to enforce consistency with known population marginals.

Let $\mathbf{X} = \{X_{ij}\}$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, $j = 1, \dots, p$, denote the seed dataset and let $\mathbf{w}_{\text{IPF}} = \{w_1, \dots, w_n\}$ be the vector of sampling weights obtained from IPF (or BIPF), ensuring that the weighted sample matches a set of target marginal distributions $\mathcal{M} = \{M_1, \dots, M_p\}$. We define a generative model \mathcal{G}_θ with parameters θ that learns the joint distribution $\mathcal{P}(X_1, \dots, X_p)$ from the (possibly reweighted) training data. Two integration strategies are possible: (i) a *pre-sampling* approach, where data are resampled according to IPF weights prior to training; and (ii) a *weighted learning* approach, where IPF weights enter directly into the loss function during training [Agyapong, 2025]. In this paper, we emphasize the pre-sampling strategy.

In the pre-sampling approach, the IPF weights are used to create a resampled training dataset whose empirical marginals already reflect the target population. Specifically, a new dataset \mathbf{X}_{IPF} of size N (the population of interest) is generated by drawing indices from the original data according to probabilities proportional to their IPF weights:

$$P(i_k = i) \propto w_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad k = 1, \dots, N.$$

Thus each observation x_i in \mathbf{X} has selection probability proportional to its adjustment weight w_i , yielding

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{IPF}} = \{x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_N}\}, \quad \text{with} \quad P(x_{i_k} = x_i) = \frac{w_i}{\sum_j w_j}.$$

Training the generative model \mathcal{G}_θ on \mathbf{X}_{IPF} implicitly incorporates the target marginal constraints into the learning process while still allowing the model to capture high-order dependencies and generate diverse synthetic agents. This procedure is summarized in Algorithm 3. The pre-sampling approach provides a simple, model-agnostic mechanism for embedding IPF-derived population constraints into generative models without modifying their architectures or training objectives.

Algorithm 3: Hybrid Synthetic Data Generation via IPF-Guided Pre-sampling

Input: Seed dataset $\mathcal{D} = [x_{ij}]$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$; $j = 1, \dots, p$); target marginal vectors $\{M_j\}_{j=1}^p$; population size $N = \sum_i (M_j)_i$ for any j .

Output: Synthetic population $\mathcal{D}_{\text{synth}}$.

Step 1: Apply IPF (or BIPF) to \mathcal{D} to obtain weights \mathbf{w}_{IPF} that align \mathcal{D} with $\{M_j\}$.

Step 2: Resample the seed data with replacement using probabilities $P(i) \propto w_i$ to form \mathcal{D}_{IPF} of size N .

Step 3: Train a generative model \mathcal{G}_θ on \mathcal{D}_{IPF} to learn an approximation $\mathcal{G}_\theta \approx \mathcal{P}(X_1, \dots, X_p)$.

Step 4: Sample new agents $\mathcal{D}_{\text{synth}} \sim \mathcal{G}_\theta$.

3. Numerical Experiments

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed methods for synthetic population generation using real-world data from the American Community Survey (ACS) Public Use Microdata Sample (PUMS). Two states—Maryland (MD) and Texas (TX)—were selected for their contrasting demographic profiles and geographic diversity. Maryland serves as a baseline for evaluating model performance under moderate dimensionality, whereas Texas provides a high-dimensional and demographically complex testbed for assessing scalability, generalizability, and

transferability. Across both states, we evaluate the performance of the proposed Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF) framework and its hybrid extension against traditional IPF-based methods and recent machine-learning-based generative models. Performance is assessed in terms of marginal fit, population diversity, and runtime efficiency.

All analyses, with the exception of the feature clustering performed using the EGAnet package [Golino and Christensen, 2024] in R [R Core Team, 2024], were conducted in Python version 3.12.3 on a 16-inch 2024 MacBook Pro equipped with 36 GB memory and an Apple M4 Max chip.

3.1 Data Sources

The datasets used for the experiments are derived from the ACS PUMS data for the states of Maryland and Texas. ACS provides individual- and household-level data that capture demographic, economic, and housing characteristics of the U.S. population, released at the PUMA level. Each PUMA lies entirely within one state and contains at least 100,000 residents.

3.1.1 Maryland Dataset

The Maryland dataset, obtained from Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024], is based on the 2012–2016 five-year ACS PUMS and includes nine categorical variables spanning demographic and economic attributes (Table 1) with 352,511 observations. This configuration results in a nine-dimensional contingency table with 58,423,680 cells, serving as a moderate-dimensional benchmark for evaluating model accuracy and computational cost.

Table 1: Variables from the 5-year Maryland ACS PUMS dataset (2012–2016).

Name	Description	Categories
AGEP	Age of person (0–99 years)	92
SEX	Gender of person	2
RAC1P	Race of person	9
ESR	Employment status	6
HINCP	Household income (past 12 months)	6
HHT	Household or family type	7
NP	Number of persons in household	7
WIF	Workers in family (past 12 months)	5
HUPAC	Presence and age of children	4
Full contingency table size: $92 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6 \times 6 \times 7 \times 7 \times 5 \times 4 = 58,423,680$		

3.1.2 Texas Dataset

For Texas, we used the 2021 five-year ACS PUMS dataset obtained directly from the U.S. Census Bureau via the MDAT platform ¹. Unlike Maryland, this dataset was designed to explore high-dimensional synthesis by including 26 attributes that jointly describe individual and household characteristics (Table 2). Records with non-positive household income or income losses exceeding \$59,999 were excluded. This dataset enables evaluation of algorithmic scalability under realistic, large-scale constraints.

¹<https://data.census.gov/app/mdat/ACSPUMS5Y2021>

Table 2: Selected variables from the 2021 5-year ACS PUMS survey data for Texas.

Name	Description	Categories (c_j)
SEX	Gender of person	2
AGEP	Age group (0–5, 5–18, 18–25, 25–35, 35–45, 45–65, 65–85, 85+)	8
RAC1P	Race of person	9
ESR	Employment status	7
HHT	Household/family type	8
HINCP	Household income (binned: [1–25k), [25k–50k), [50k–75k), [75k–100k), [100k–200k), \$200k+)	6
RMSP	Number of rooms in housing unit	16
BDSP	Number of bedrooms	6
RNTM	Meals included in rent	3
HICOV	Health insurance coverage status	2
NWLK	Looking for work status	4
JWRIP	Vehicle occupancy	5
NP	Number of persons in household	9
WIF	Workers in family (past 12 months)	5
HUPAC	Household presence/age of children	5
TEN	Tenure of housing unit	5
SCHL	Educational attainment	25
WKW	Weeks worked (past 12 months)	7
WKL	When last worked	4
VEH	Number of vehicles	7
TEL	Telephone service availability	3
SCH	School enrollment status	4
HHL	Household language spoken	6
ENG	English-speaking ability	5
CIT	Citizenship status	5
COW	Class of worker	10
Full contingency table size: $\prod_{j=1}^{26} c_j \approx 5.53 \times 10^{19}$		

The full contingency table implied by the 26 categorical variables in Table 2 contains $\prod_{j=1}^{26} c_j = 55,306,395,648,000,000,000$ cells ($\approx 5.53 \times 10^{19}$). Storing such a table in memory would require an astronomical amount of space on the order of hundreds of exabytes if each cell were stored as a single double-precision value (8 bytes). This scale renders the direct application of classical IPF or any approach requiring full joint table construction computationally infeasible even on modern high-performance systems. These constraints strongly motivate the development of scalable alternatives such as the proposed Blockwise IPF and its hybrid extensions, which operate on lower-dimensional margins without explicitly constructing the full joint space.

3.2 Synthetic Population Generation Framework

Following the experimental protocol of Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024], we conduct synthetic population generation across three geographic levels: (1) state, (2) county, and (3) Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs)—statistical geographic units defined by the U.S. Census Bureau, each representing at least 100,000 residents U.S. Census Bureau. PUMAs serve as the smallest geographic level at which ACS microdata are released, providing an anonymized yet representative subset of the U.S. population.

Our evaluation spans both intra-state synthesis and multiple transferability tasks. For Maryland, we perform replication and benchmarking using the same nine-variable dataset presented in Table

1 as used by Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024]. The first set of experiments involved reproducing the population structure of the State of Maryland by splitting the data into a source (think of this as the reference micro-sample data available) and a target population from which the aggregated marginal distributions are obtained. In practice, all that we know about the population is the aggregated information, which we seek to disaggregate using the micro-sample. Two settings consisting of a 10% and a 20% source data were considered to assess how sample size impacts performance. The remaining 90% and 80% sets are aggregated to form the known marginal distributions of the corresponding populations used as the target constraints. To challenge the IPF fitting process, we employed a non-representative splitting strategy that ensured the source and target sets differed not only in size but also in the marginal distributions of the variables.

We then assess horizontal transferability by training our models on one county (or PUMA) as the source and applying them to another at the same geographic resolution level as the target population. These spatial transfer settings closely reflect real-world scenarios in which representative sample data from one geographic area are used to infer or synthesize population characteristics in another region that shares a similar dependency structure.

To further examine scalability, we replicate these experiments in Texas using a larger feature set (26 variables listed in 2) directly drawn from the ACS.

3.3 Methods Evaluated

We benchmarked the proposed Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF) framework against classical and modern population synthesis methods, including both traditional IPF-based approaches and generative-model-based synthesizers. All methods were implemented in Python using publicly available libraries or in-house implementations.

- **Independent Sampling (Baseline):** A simple random sampling procedure used as a baseline. It serves as a lower-bound benchmark, providing a reference for assessing the benefit of marginal alignment and dependency modeling.
- **Classical IPF and IPU:** The standard Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) algorithm, implemented using the `ipfn` package², and its household-person variant, the Iterative Proportional Updating (IPU)³ method [Ye et al., 2009] were included as traditional benchmarks. IPU is a fast and an efficient
- **Proposed Blockwise IPF (BIPF) Framework:** Our primary contribution, evaluated in two formulations:
 1. *Naive BIPF (N-BIPF)* — applies IPF independently across variable blocks, combining block-level weights multiplicatively to approximate the global solution.
 2. *Sequential BIPF (S-BIPF)* — applies IPF iteratively across blocks, reweighting the micro dataset sequentially after each block adjustment.

Both versions were evaluated for computational efficiency and marginal fitting accuracy, especially under high-dimensional settings.

- **Bayesian Network (BN):** A probabilistic graphical model that captures conditional dependencies among variables, implemented using the `pgmpy`⁴ library. Bayesian networks serve as an interpretable, generative baseline capable of learning joint dependencies directly from data.
- **Hybrid Methods:** Two hybrid generative strategies were assessed:

²<https://github.com/Dirguis/ipfn>

³<https://pypi.org/project/pyipu/>

⁴<https://pgmpy.org/started/base.html>

1. *BN Copula*⁵: A Bayesian network–based synthesizer with a Gaussian copula normalization step introduced by Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024].
2. *IPF-Based Hybrid (Proposed)*: Combines IPF/IPU- or BIPF-derived weights with a generative Bayesian network that leverages IPF for marginal alignment and BN for dependency preservation and out-of-sample diversity.

The comparative evaluation thus spans traditional, blockwise, and hybrid formulations, which allows us to quantify gains in scalability, marginal accuracy, and structural fidelity introduced by the proposed framework.

3.4 Performance Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate the proposed methods along three key dimensions: (1) computational complexity (measured by runtime), (2) accuracy of marginal distribution alignment, and (3) preservation of dependency structure and diversity.

3.4.1 Computation time

Computational complexity was quantified via wall-clock runtime (in seconds) required for each method to complete the synthetic population generation process. Runtime was recorded using Python’s `timeit.default_timer()` (based on `time.perf_counter()`), which offers high-resolution timing. As discussed earlier, the proposed Blockwise IPF (BIPF) framework is designed to alleviate the exponential runtime and memory burden of classical IPF in high-dimensional contexts. Hence, the runtime metric serves as a key indicator of the scalability gains introduced by BIPF.

3.4.2 Accuracy in marginal distribution fit

We used the *Standardized Root Mean Squared Error (SRMSE)*, a widely adopted measure in synthetic population generation studies Borysov et al. [2018], Sun and Erath [2015], Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024], to assess the fidelity of marginal alignment between the synthetic and target distributions. Following Jutras-Dubé et al. [2024], we projected the SRMSE over subsets of p variables so that when $p > 1$, SRMSE quantifies the fit of higher-order dependencies, while for $p = 1$ it captures univariate marginal alignment. Lower SRMSE values indicate closer agreement between the synthetic and target distributions.

3.4.3 Mean Absolute Correlation Difference (MACD)

To evaluate how well each method preserves the dependency structure of the original data, we introduce the *Mean Absolute Correlation Difference (MACD)* metric. MACD measures the average absolute deviation in pairwise correlations between two datasets.

Let $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times p}$ and $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 \times p}$ be two datasets with p variables. Define their correlation matrices as

$$R^X = [r_{ij}^X]_{p \times p}, \quad R^Y = [r_{ij}^Y]_{p \times p}.$$

The unnormalized MACD is

$$MACD = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{I}} |r_{ij}^X - r_{ij}^Y|, \tag{7}$$

⁵<https://github.com/PascalJD/copulapopgen>

where $\mathcal{I} = \{(i, j) \mid 1 \leq i < j \leq p\}$, and $|\mathcal{I}| = \frac{p(p-1)}{2}$, by symmetry. To standardize interpretation, we normalize MACD to lie in $[0, 1]$:

$$MACD = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{p(p-1)} \sum_{i < j} |r_{ij}^X - r_{ij}^Y|, & \text{for correlations in } [0, 1], \\ \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \sum_{i < j} |r_{ij}^X - r_{ij}^Y|, & \text{for correlations in } [-1, 1]. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Values of $MACD$ close to zero indicate high preservation of pairwise dependencies, while higher values indicate greater divergence. Note that MACD captures only pairwise dependencies and does not account for higher-order interactions. We used the Cramer’s V coefficient with bias correction as the correlation measure to compute the MACD and reported it as $MACD_C$.

3.4.4 Diversity Score

Beyond marginal accuracy and dependency preservation, it is essential to assess whether the synthesizer generates realistic yet novel data points rather than replicating the training data. To this end, we use the *NewRowSynthesis* metric⁶ from the SDMetrics library (part of the Synthetic Data Vault suite), which measures the proportion of unique records in the synthetic dataset by computing one minus the fraction of synthetic rows that exactly match rows in the real data. A score of 1 indicates complete novelty (no matches), while 0 indicates full duplication of the training data.

3.5 Feature Clustering for the BIPF Framework

We employed the Louvain community detection algorithm on the variable association network derived from the source population data to define the block structures needed for the implementation of the proposed Blockwise IPF (BIPF) methods. This procedure was conducted using the Exploratory Graph Analysis (EGA) framework Golino and Christensen [2024], as implemented in the EGAnet R package. The EGA approach constructs a partial correlation network based on pairwise associations among variables and applies community detection methods (such as Louvain) to identify clusters of features that exhibit stronger within-group dependencies relative to between-group dependencies. These clusters are subsequently treated as independent blocks in the BIPF procedure. The size of the edges (edge weight) in Figures 2 and 3 is a measure of the partial correlation between two variables after accounting for the influence of all other variables in the network.

For the Maryland ACS PUMS dataset, the Louvain–EGA procedure yielded two stable communities, forming the basis of our blockwise implementation:

$$G_1 = \{\text{HINCP, SEX, WIF, HHT}\}, \quad G_2 = \{\text{NP, AGE, RAC1P, ESR, HUPAC}\}.$$

Figure 2 depicts the resulting feature network and community structure. Notably, this grouping remained consistent across data at the state, county, and PUMA levels, suggesting that the underlying dependency patterns among variables are reasonably preserved across these geographic scales.

⁶<https://docs.sdv.dev/sdmetrics/metrics/metrics-in-beta/newrowsynthesis>

the state level, which tested the ability of the synthesizers to reproduce the population structure of the Maryland ACS data from a limited but representative sample (10% and 20%) taken from the population.

In addition to within-population synthesis, we evaluated the spatial transferability of synthetic population generation methods—i.e., their ability to generalize from a source region to a demographically distinct target region. Two transfer scenarios were tested (see Table 4): (1) using data from Anne Arundel County with 22,345 observations as the source and Baltimore City consisting of 27,103 observations as the target population, and (2) using PUMA 1201 (in Anne Arundel County with 6533 data points) as source and PUMA 804 (in Baltimore City with 6049 data points) as the target.

Table 3: Performance of synthetic population generation methods for Maryland at the state level.

	Method	SRMSE ₁	SRMSE ₂	SRMSE ₃	SRMSE ₄	MACD _C	Diversity	Runtime (s)
10% Source → 90% Target								
Baseline	Independent	0.271	0.726	1.526	2.910	0.190	0.929	743.430
Non-Hybrid	IPF	0.031	0.201	0.613	1.661	0.053	0.000	198.395
	IPU	0.006	0.049	0.172	0.504	0.022	0.000	24.821
	S-BIPF	0.012	0.063	0.196	0.545	0.022	0.000	1.521
	N-BIPF	0.051	0.122	0.274	0.641	0.023	0.000	0.459
	BN	0.272	0.822	2.202	5.527	0.205	0.615	1.136
Hybrid	BN Copula	0.004	0.385	1.554	4.680	0.189	0.845	19.611
	IPF BN	0.036	0.359	1.570	5.167	0.187	0.625	200.898
	IPU BN	0.010	0.154	0.622	1.970	0.157	0.597	27.518
	S-BIPF BN	0.016	0.102	0.369	1.176	0.163	0.604	3.736
	N-BIPF BN	0.056	0.258	0.851	2.431	0.176	0.617	2.890
20% Source → 80% Target								
Baseline	Independent	0.277	0.742	1.553	2.953	0.190	0.909	1269.882
Non-Hybrid	IPF	0.007	0.040	0.135	0.390	0.021	0.000	129.583
	IPU	0.004	0.039	0.133	0.387	0.021	0.000	50.120
	S-BIPF	0.013	0.056	0.165	0.445	0.020	0.000	1.571
	N-BIPF	0.051	0.118	0.250	0.552	0.022	0.000	0.668
	BN	0.276	0.997	2.668	6.423	0.179	0.484	1.146
Hybrid	BN Copula	0.004	0.502	1.874	5.406	0.160	0.778	18.071
	IPF BN	0.009	0.128	0.548	1.749	0.168	0.531	131.794
	IPU BN	0.008	0.125	0.522	1.689	0.157	0.527	52.290
	S-BIPF BN	0.015	0.097	0.355	1.132	0.166	0.528	3.605
	N-BIPF BN	0.050	0.230	0.750	2.138	0.174	0.544	2.867

Table 4: Spatial transferability at the same geographic level results in synthetic population generation from one region to another.

	Method	SRMSE ₁	SRMSE ₂	SRMSE ₃	SRMSE ₄	MACD _C	Diversity	Runtime (s)
Anne Arundel County → Baltimore City								
Baseline	Independent	0.579	1.274	2.224	3.710	0.193	0.959	43.721
Non-Hybrid	IPF	0.015	0.193	0.605	1.563	0.032	0.000	119.243
	IPU	0.019	0.194	0.602	1.553	0.032	0.000	19.848
	S-BIPF	0.059	0.275	0.746	1.848	0.036	0.000	0.258
	N-BIPF	0.259	0.584	1.215	2.598	0.044	0.000	0.262
	BN	0.577	1.672	4.052	9.242	0.208	0.628	0.208
Hybrid	BN Copula	0.014	0.557	2.095	5.960	0.179	0.956	1.919
	IPF BN	0.024	0.290	1.127	3.343	0.175	0.789	119.491
	IPU BN	0.030	0.299	1.216	4.107	0.184	0.817	20.076
	S-BIPF BN	0.058	0.401	1.493	4.688	0.183	0.844	0.469
	N-BIPF BN	0.260	0.790	2.100	5.242	0.178	0.788	0.502
PUMA 1201 → PUMA 804								
Baseline	Independent	0.609	1.317	2.396	4.291	0.188	0.982	3.634
Non-Hybrid	IPF	0.033	0.352	1.070	2.771	0.056	0.000	154.567
	IPU	0.030	0.341	1.053	2.746	0.058	0.000	8.775
	S-BIPF	0.055	0.387	1.156	2.999	0.062	0.000	0.144
	N-BIPF	0.349	0.876	1.970	4.482	0.080	0.000	0.132
	BN	0.602	1.742	4.544	11.490	0.207	0.824	0.097
Hybrid	BN Copula	0.030	0.831	3.154	9.508	0.183	0.989	0.512
	IPF BN	0.054	0.683	2.713	8.787	0.178	0.925	154.672
	IPU BN	0.046	0.594	2.413	7.958	0.185	0.911	8.877
	S-BIPF BN	0.063	0.589	2.368	7.785	0.220	0.921	0.255
	N-BIPF BN	0.331	1.148	3.367	9.303	0.208	0.886	0.240

3.6.2 Texas Experiments

The experiments involved synthesizing a population over 26 socio-demographic and household variables as the most challenging modeling settings considered in this work. Table 5 shows results for the spatial transferability population synthesis from Dallas County to Dallas City County and again from Dallas County, but this time to El Paso County.

In this set of synthetic population generation experiments, the limitations of traditional IPF methods became particularly evident in these high-dimensional regimes. The standard IPF implementation from the `ipfn`[Forthomme, 2021] package could not be executed due to severe memory constraints, even on a 2024 MacBook Pro equipped with 36 GB RAM and an Apple M4 Max processor.

Table 5: Texas transferability experiments: synthetic population generation from Dallas County to Dallas City and El Paso County Targets.

	Method	SRMSE ₁	SRMSE ₂	SRMSE ₃	SRMSE ₄	MACD _C	Diversity	Runtime (s)
Dallas County → Dallas City								
Baseline	Independent	0.214	0.696	1.583	3.170	0.156	1.000	142.457
	IPU	0.010	0.092	0.281	0.707	0.023	0.000	67.326
	S-BIPF	0.051	0.167	0.421	0.988	0.034	0.000	0.703
	N-BIPF	0.340	0.767	1.490	2.826	0.040	0.000	0.530
Non-Hybrid	BN	0.211	0.618	1.531	3.582	0.138	0.998	1.426
	BN Copula	0.009	0.266	0.936	2.578	0.133	1.000	6.779
	IPU BN	0.016	0.172	0.614	1.764	0.150	0.998	69.134
	S-BIPF BN	0.048	0.213	0.651	1.751	0.154	0.997	2.610
Hybrid	N-BIPF BN	0.340	0.878	2.013	4.474	0.147	0.995	2.356
Dallas County → El Paso County								
Baseline	Independent	0.210	0.674	1.508	2.948	0.156	1.000	154.242
	IPU	0.010	0.118	0.356	0.874	0.022	0.000	78.438
	S-BIPF	0.078	0.240	0.579	1.319	0.031	0.000	0.730
	N-BIPF	0.201	0.502	1.069	2.240	0.042	0.000	0.540
Non-Hybrid	BN	0.205	0.595	1.429	3.224	0.138	1.000	1.433
	BN Copula	0.012	0.182	0.629	1.704	0.134	1.000	7.145
	IPU BN	0.019	0.147	0.499	1.365	0.147	0.998	80.338
	S-BIPF BN	0.082	0.273	0.729	1.806	0.135	0.998	2.665
Hybrid	N-BIPF BN	0.202	0.574	1.399	3.274	0.153	0.989	2.504

4. Discussion

Across all experiments, the results demonstrate that the proposed Blockwise Iterative Proportional Fitting (BIPF) framework and its hybrid extensions successfully address the scalability and generalizability limitations inherent in traditional IPF-based population synthesis methods.

4.1 Performance on Moderate-Dimensional Data (Maryland)

For the Maryland experiments, which represent a moderate-dimensional setting (9 variables), both Sequential BIPF (S-BIPF) and Naive BIPF (N-BIPF) closely approximated the performance of standard IPF and IPU in terms of marginal fit (SRMSE₁) and dependency preservation (SRMSE₂–SRMSE₄, MACD_C). However, the BIPF variants achieved these results at a fraction of the computational cost. At the state level, S-BIPF completed synthesis in approximately 1.5 seconds compared to over 198 seconds for standard IPF and 25 seconds for IPU.

In terms of marginal distribution alignment, SRMSE values for S-BIPF were consistently below 0.02 for univariate fits and below 0.20 for multivariate projections, indicating high accuracy. Dependency preservation (MACD_C) remained comparable to IPU (≈ 0.02), confirming that partitioning did not distort key correlation structures. While the hybrid BIPF–BN variants introduced marginal increases in MACD ($\approx 0.16 - 0.18$), they substantially improved diversity (≈ 0.60) over pure IPF or IPU, which by definition generate no novel instances.

Spatial transferability results (Table 4) further reveal that S-BIPF and its hybrid extension retain reasonable fidelity even when synthesizing populations for demographically distinct target regions. Although SRMSE values rose modestly due to cross-region shifts, BIPF variants maintained performance competitive with IPF and IPU, while requiring less than 1s of runtime. These results underscore the flexibility of the blockwise formulation for domain adaptation tasks.

4.2 Performance on High-Dimensional Data (Texas)

The Texas experiments, involving 26 variables, provided a rigorous test of scalability. Here, the standard IPF algorithm could not be executed due to memory exhaustion, even on a 36 GB workstation. In contrast, BIPF—especially the sequential variant—completed synthesis efficiently, with runtime improvements of one to two orders of magnitude relative to IPU while maintaining competitive accuracy.

In particular, S-BIPF achieved SRMSE and $MACD_C$ values comparable to IPU but with around a $100\times$ reduction in runtime. The naive variant (N-BIPF), though faster, showed slightly higher SRMSE and $MACD$ values, consistent with the trade-off between independence assumptions and structural accuracy. Hybrid models (S-BIPF–BN and IPU–BN) achieved the best balance between marginal distribution alignment and diversity, yielding nearly perfect diversity scores without substantial compromise in $MACD$.

5. Conclusion

This study introduced a scalable and hybrid framework for synthetic population generation built upon the classical Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) foundation. The proposed Blockwise IPF (BIPF) framework adopts a block-coordinate-like approach to partition the variable space into statistically coherent groups and performs proportional fitting within each block to drastically improve computational efficiency while preserving accuracy in marginal distributions and dependency structures. Through extensive experiments using ACS PUMS data for Maryland and Texas, BIPF and its hybrid extensions demonstrated:

- Comparable or superior accuracy to traditional IPF and IPU methods in moderate-dimensional settings.
- Two orders-of-magnitude speed improvements in high-dimensional scenarios where standard IPF fails to execute.
- Enhanced adaptability to spatial transfer contexts.
- High diversity and dependency preservation when coupled with generative models.

These findings collectively affirm the potential of blockwise and hybrid strategies for advancing large-scale population synthesis, survey calibration, and related applications. Future research will explore alternative block construction techniques, parallelized implementations for high-performance computing environments, and the integration of deep generative architectures (e.g., VAEs, CTGANs) under marginal constraints.

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